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you? :)*

Elders learning English for Europe
2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465

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ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE

THE TURKISH CASE

This study investigates motivational factors and language learning strategies involved in the process of learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL) in the elderly. This needs' analysis report is part of the implementation of ERASMUS+ project nr 2021-1-PL01-KA220-ADU-000033465.

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ELDERS LEARNING ENGLISH FOR EUROPE

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INTRODUCTION

People have begun to live longer, and their active life notions and activities have gone through changes. Greater life expectancy is an important issue that challenges countries around the globe. The ageing of populations affects all aspects of human life in social, financial, cultural, and political domains. One of the important issues of the 21st century is understanding and providing for ageing.

Currently, one out of every ten people is aged 60 or above. It is estimated that by 2050 one out of five people will be aged 60 or older. By 2150, one out of every three people is estimated to be 60 and over. With lower birth rates and higher life expectancy, the proportion of the elderly is already one in four in some developed countries (Erişen, 2010). According to the United Nations (UN), the 21st century will be the century of the old, which is also referred the “silver tsunami” (Boulton-Lewis, 2010).

The developing countries are also facing the reality of the ageing issue. Turkey is among the developing countries category and has a relatively younger population. However, having an ageing population has been on its agenda in recent years (Erişen, 2010) and the country is experiencing a new demographic structure. Starting from the year 2020, the proportion of this group of population is expected to be 20%, with an expected increase in the following years.

Active participation of elderly individuals in social life brings many advantages not only for them but also for the societies they live in. Various programs and projects around the world have investigated how and why elderly people should be involved in social life through active living. This project focuses on the learning of elderly individuals with a specific focus on learning English for travel purposes and presents findings obtained from the questionnaire administered for determining their needs on this issue.

SOCIAL INCLUSION OF ELDERLY INDIVIDUALS

Social inclusion of elderly individuals in life is of vital importance not only for those individuals but also for countries. The right of older people to live in dignity, promoting their independence and participation in social, economic and civic life is indicated by the Council of the European Union. It is recommended that older individuals should remain active as citizens, workers, consumers, careers, and volunteers. In this regard, the engagement of elderly individuals in education and life-long training activities is of great importance for their well-being.

According to the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA), there are seven types of relationships and services as meaningful indicators of the social inclusion/exclusion of elderly individuals. There are listed as follows:

- a) Social relationships: contact with family and friends
- b) Cultural and leisure activities: going to the cinema or theatre, etc.
- c) Civic activities: voluntary work, voting, membership in interest groups, etc.
- d) Basic services: health and social services, shops
- e) Neighborhood: safety and friendliness of people in the neighborhood
- f) Financial products: bank accounts and pensions
- g) Material Goods: Consumer durables, central heating, etc.

Depending on the country where they live as well as the socio-economic and personal conditions they have, elderly individuals are excluded on one or some of the items mentioned above. Some disadvantaged groups are reported to face multiple or severe exclusion; namely are excluded on three or more dimensions. According to a report published in England, 1.2 million people aged 50 or more face multiple exclusion, with the intensification of the condition for people beyond the age of 75 (Age concern England 2008).

Social isolation and exclusion have been reported to be associated with many emotional and physical risk factors such as depression, anxiety, high blood pressure, mortality, alcoholism and drug abuse, cognitive decline, dementia, long-term illnesses, etc. Social activity is encouraged to combat senior isolation, and there are some ways to encourage social activity for elderly individuals. Designing care plans depending on individuals and their preferences is a good way of involving elderly people in social life. Some recommendations for involving these age groups include:

- increasing time spent with them,
- encouraging family visits,
- suggesting joining a club or volunteering, and
- encouraging outside activities.

TRAVEL AND THE ELDERLY

Integration of this population into society is an important issue. Elderly individuals tend to isolate themselves from society as they get older; however, they should be helped to have more social value by experiencing active ageing. When the required conditions are provided, ageing is reported to demonstrate a relationship with productivity. The WHO adopted the term “active ageing” in the late 1990s. The term is believed to convey a more inclusive message than “healthy ageing” and aims to help to recognize the factors affecting how individuals and populations age. The term refers to being physically and mentally active, engaging in learning, working, and actively participating in family, and community life. Active ageing is multidimensional, and education and learning are assumed to be important factors.

Travelling is part of active ageing. Older people's mobility is believed to promote social inclusion and active participation in life. Studies show that the travel motivations of older adults stimulate their travel actions, and their travels are reported to contribute to greater life satisfaction. Travel has the potential to provide older adults with recreational opportunities, maintain social and physical activities, and satisfy socio-psychological needs. Some of these needs include but are not limited to rest, relaxation, social interaction, learning, and excitement. By remaining active in later life, elderly people can maintain social roles and functioning, which can further contribute to better physical and mental health and life satisfaction. Travel is an important factor that helps to achieve these. Participation in travel activities can support continued involvement in different domains of life as well as interactions with other people,

Older adults' travel motivations:

- stimulate travel actions and enhance self-esteem and social recognition,
- provide escape and relaxation, and
- promote learning and discovery.

Through travel, elderly individuals become interested in escaping from daily routines and improving self-esteem and social recognition. Little details such as preparing travel information and places to visit before departure, having conversations with others about travel itineraries, arranging accommodation, and sharing the joy of travel are reported to provide older adults with opportunities for social participation and interaction with others as well as sense of pleasure and satisfaction.

LEARNING AND THE ELDERLY

Learning is a life-long process, and the benefits of continued learning have been well-documented through studies conducted worldwide. It is an important component of active ageing. Moreover, a positive relationship was reported between health and learning (Ross & Mirowsky, 1999; Hammond, 2002, 2004; Narushima, 2008). There are 12 possible learning benefits categorized into three forms of capital as follows:

- a) human capital: human capital is for skills training or retraining
- b) social capital: social capital is for relationships and social networking
- c) identity capital: identity capital is for personal development, interests, and other life pursuits.

Elder individuals who are engaged in lifelong learning are reported to have positive experiences in several areas such as enjoyment of life, increased confidence, self-satisfaction, and ability to cope. Particularly with the rapid changes in technology, the need for elderly individuals' learning has become a must. Elderly individuals who continue learning are believed to keep up with modern technology and maintain their quality of life by enhancing their self-sufficiency and coping strategies. Self-sufficiency helps them to deal with health and social relationship-related challenges. Less mental decline is another very important benefit of learning and active use of the brain. Neurological research conducted in the last two decades shows that mental activity performed in old age:

- boosts intellectual power,
- helps to maintain mental function, and
- reverse memory decline (Withnall, 2000; Kotulak, 1997).

Studies also showed that elderly individuals who are stimulated mentally have a little decline in memory and continue intellectual growth even in their late lives (Wolf, 2009). Although they learn more slowly and need more practice, elders are reported to have stronger motivation to learn. They are also reported to want to be engaged with continued learning due to reasons as follows:

- exercising the mind,
- staying mentally stimulated and active,
- attaining certain life goals, and
- simply never stopping learning.

Various studies in the literature have investigated what elders want to learn, which indicated a wide range of topics including health, safety, leisure, transportation, technology, new activities,

and leisure interests to keep up-to-date with new technology and make an effort to learn new things, discover new talents, acquire new skills, and take up new vocations.

In essence, continued learning can help people gain socioeconomic, psychological, and sociopolitical benefits. These benefits are believed to contribute to the well-being of elderly individuals. Given the advantages of continued learning, elderly individuals should be provided with accessible opportunities for elder learning. These kinds of opportunities can be formal, semiformal, and informal learning provided by organizations established for various purposes.

Preferences of elders also demonstrate differences regarding how and where they want to learn. Although some of them prefer organized courses and formalized activities, some others prefer informal learning such as reading, conversation, and watching educational materials. This diversity in their preferences indicates the need for meeting older learners' needs as lifelong learners. Educators and program designers should keep in mind that as they age, people have differing learning needs and expectations. Their needs for enrolling- and not enrolling- in programs should be understood well. Elders are reported to be engaged in learning mainly for two motivation types which include expressive and instrumental motivation.

While expressive motivation refers to personal development and social relations, instrumental motivation refers to work, career, and skills training. According to a survey, people aged 55 have the following reasons to be engaged in learning:

- meeting people,
- filling up time,
- learning something new,
- making life more meaningful,
- developing personal interests and hobbies.

These items indicate that elders are engaged in learning for intrinsic rather than extrinsic reasons. A study conducted in Turkey investigated the use of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC) and found that the number of users who are aged over 65 had more than doubled since 2000. These studies and many others conducted in different parts of the world demonstrate the need elderly individuals feel for continuing to learn, which calls for the programs that address these needs.

ELDERS AND LEARNING ENGLISH

The role of travel in active ageing and elderly people's well-being is obvious. When travel is considered, one is not limited to one country merely. Hence, the language issue is considered to be a factor that needs to be taken into consideration. No matter what country people visit, one language is the key to communication: English.

With the globalization of the world, English has gone beyond being a particular language of a country or nation. It is now a multi-national, multi-cultural, and multi-functional language. More and more people in the world have mastered English, which made the number of people who use it as a foreign language greater than the number of people who use it as their first language. As a result, English is the language of the whole world. Therefore, learning a foreign language should be one of the goals of traveling elder people.

Most studies focus on how children, adolescents, and young adults learn languages. While the literature covers a substantial number of studies on the learning, foreign language learning needs, characteristics, and strategies of individuals from younger age groups, despite its importance, elderly individuals' learning English has not been investigated much in the literature.

The influences of bilingualism have been demonstrated in the literature. Learning a foreign language is reported to enable cognitive decline or delay the onset of dementia (Bak, Nissan, Allerhand, & Deary, 4 2014). Thus, there is a need to raise awareness of EFL teachers in creating special EFL programs for Senior Citizens, a population that inevitably keeps growing. Learning a second language has been shown to enable remarkable health improvement when they learn a second language at the age of 70 years and ahead (Conde, 2020).

There are some advantages and challenges of teaching and learning English in the population of elderly individuals. From the teachers' side, some advantages can be listed as follows:

- Elderly individuals have rich life experiences that offer different ideas and opinions regarding a wide range of areas. The richness of this experience may put the teacher in the learner position.
- Elderly individuals are not motivated to be engaged in learning to obtain a certificate or qualification. This factor makes teaching more motivational for the teacher.
- The main purpose of elderly individuals in the foreign language process could be wanting to socialize, enjoying the process, or becoming active again. These characteristics enable a great advantage for the teachers (Findsen & Formosa, 2011).
- Elderly individuals challenge teachers because they need a more dynamic methodology with life experiences they have had.

Advantages for the learners can be listed as follows:

- elderly learners' quality of life increases with the learning experience
- with the learning experience they have, elderly individuals could develop critical thinking skills, including reflecting and acting on social problems.
- they could participate in social movements and push for wider cultural and political transformations.
- social integration gained through the language learning process promotes life satisfaction, alleviates the sense of loneliness, and contributes to physical and mental health.
- participating in a language classroom could help elderly individuals to create good friendships and keep them distracted.

Programs designed for elderly individuals' learning a foreign language should consider these factors.

METHODS

Elderly individuals living in Turkey were administered a questionnaire to explore their views and ideas about learning English as a foreign language for travel purposes. The questions asked aimed to explore the main reasons and motivations for traveling as well as learning English as a foreign language. A total of 51 Individuals responded to the questionnaire.

FINDINGS

This section presents the questionnaire results.

1. What is your age?

2. What is your gender?

As the figures above demonstrate, 51% of the participants were aged 61 to 70 years old and 31,4% were aged 51 to 60 years old. While 60,8% were females, 39,2% were males.

3. Where do you live?

4 Are you currently...?

The questionnaire was administered to older adults living in Turkey, so all the participants reported to live in Turkey and more than half of them were retired (58.8%).

5. Size of the place of residence

6. What is your preferred form of tourism?

While 76.5% of the participants lived in a city with more than 500,000 inhabitants, they agreed with beach tourism, and cultural tourism options most. They were not interested in wildlife tourism or adventure tourism.

7. Who accompanies you in your trip?

8. Which of the following barriers limit you from travelling?

Almost none of the participants travel with people they met via the internet. A great majority of the respondents traveled with partners, friends, and family. Some barriers include lack of financial resources, and health problems, but lack of time was not a problem.

9. Difficulty in learning a foreign language is:

10. To learn a foreign language would you use

Remembering words was seen as the greatest difficulty for the participants, which was followed by fear of speaking or fear of making mistakes from time to time. However, most of the participants disagreed with the reluctance factor to learn foreign languages. They also indicated that they would use smartphones, laptops, and web pages for learning, but printed books or board games were not preferred much.

11. Because of COVID-19 - If you could choose, which way would be the best for you to learn a language?

12. Have you ever travelled to a foreign country?

Almost all of the participants indicated that they would probably use web pages, e-learning platforms, mobile phone applications, CD-DVD, or written materials for learning a language. More than half of the participants (64.7%) traveled to a foreign country before.

13. Would you be interested to learn English?

12. Why would you study English?

Almost all of the respondents want to learn English (96,1%). Their motivation to learn included interest in language and interest in the culture mostly. Socializing with people and shopping were preferred less.

15 Use of travel apps as:

16. What should be included in the prospective learning material to improve your English?

The use of travel applications included mostly getting information about the destination and discovering new places. Most of the participants are interested in learning materials that enable learning by themselves and watching video materials.

17 What do you think is lacking in the electronic materials used for English language learning?

18 Would you like to have your own application adapted to your needs to help you in your trips?

The participants think that the existing materials do not have a connection to internet resources, are not easy to use, and do not contain sufficient visual materials. They would like to have their own app tailored to their specific needs.

The participants would like to have:

- videos such as YouTube
- promotion of visual learning materials through social media
- interaction and speaking practice
- effective learning and teaching and guiding exercises
- self-learning

CONCLUSION

The population of elderly individuals has been growing throughout the world, and Turkey is no exception. Although Turkey has a relatively younger population, the proportion of the elderly has been increasing and is expected to continue increasing in the following years. Hence, the social inclusion of elderly individuals is an important issue.

Being engaged in social life and learning are two prominent components of active ageing. Both of them help elderly individuals feel better and increase their quality of life. Elderly individuals enjoy learning new knowledge and skills that make their life more meaningful. Learning a foreign language can be considered one type of learning that can be considered in this category.

Tourism is an important part of elderly individuals' life. The participants who responded to the questionnaire in Turkey were interested in the beach and cultural tourism rather than other types of tourism. Cultural exchange requires traveling to other countries and speaking a common language. Learning English could serve the purpose of cultural exchange in this age group.

The respondents in Turkey were not interested in traveling with people they met via the internet. They were interested in traveling with people they know such as friends and relatives. The process of planning their travel and learning something about the destinations, culture, and other details about their travel could help elderly individuals to feel good and increase their quality of life. This process could be enriched with a foreign language learning experience.

Some barriers prevent elderly individuals from being engaged in travel activities. Lack of financial resources and health problems can be considered barriers. Pensions are not very high for many retired people in Turkey. Travel expenses have become extra problematic, particularly after the Covid-19 pandemic. Health considerations could also prevent elderly individuals from traveling to other countries with unfamiliar health systems. On the other hand, lack of time is not a barrier for elderly individuals. Elderly individuals who do not have severe health problems or who have enough financial resources could enjoy traveling to increase their quality of life.

Everyone learns their own language with a fair degree of success; however, foreign language learning processes may not be that easy for many people including elderly individuals. Determination of common problems in learning a foreign language could help to eliminate these problems. Remembering words and fear of speaking are the common problems experienced by many elderly individuals. Education programs should consider how to make these learning processes more effective for elderly individuals.

Elderly individuals who have time seem to be willing to learn a foreign language. This willingness accompanied by life experiences can be utilized as an effective source of learning. In addition, technological devices have been dominating our lives, and the life of elderly individuals are not different. Learning materials provided through digital sources and devices seem to attract elderly

individuals' attention more. Similar to other age groups, elderly individuals also find the sources provided through web pages, applications, etc. more effective in terms of various aspects.

Elderly individuals' motivation to learn English is intrinsic rather than extrinsic, which makes their learning and teaching processes different. Exploring the culture of a country and learning the language merely for learning about that language are important factors that motivate elderly individuals in their learning processes.

Getting information about the destination and discovering new places are among the main motivations of elderly individuals. Language learning materials could be designed to include these in their content. Materials that enable learning by themselves and watching video materials are interesting for elderly individuals. Video materials that include listening and speaking activities and visuals that help them learn and remember vocabulary better are important factors.

Existing materials do not seem to be effective and sufficient for elderly individuals due to a lack of audio and visual materials specific to their level. Therefore, there is a need to design apps tailored to their specific needs. Videos, the content presented on social media websites, interaction and speaking practice, and self-learning can be listed among the methods found effective by elderly individuals.

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